

Consumption of Electricity by Vending Machines

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ABSTRACT

The project has been completed in December 2013 and performed in Danish. The second page of this summary is a guideline in Danish for Campus Service at DTU to improve the handling of vending machines at DTU. Though the focus of the project has been national as well.

In Denmark there are estimated to be more than 20.000 soda vending machines and each of them consumes in the scale of 3.500 kWh every year. The short term potential for improvement alone will be able to reduce the electricity consumption by a factor of two. The outcome of the project has been a solution for implementing a service/system. The documentation is a brief final report containing 13 pages together with an article published in the Danish scientific newspaper "Ingeniøren" and a five minutes video posted on youtube.

ENVIRONMENT IMPROVEMENT POTENTIAL

FAKTOR

Short term: 2
(timer & placement)

Long term: 4
(new automat)

Future: 10
(instacool)

LINKS:

Article:
<http://ing.dk/artikel/en-sodavandsautomat-drikker-stroem-som-en-trevaerelses-lejlighed-164833>

Video:
<http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=z4YiNZ6thp0>